

On the Variation of the Surface Tension of Aqueous Solutions of certain Dyestuffs with Time.

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The growth of films on the surface of aqueous solutions of a number of organic dyes was first recorded by Rhode (*Ann. Phys.*, 1906, 19, 935). His method consisted in the suspension of a sheet of metal in the dye solution by a fine wire. Torsion was applied until the surface was broken. The angle of torsion was a measure of the thickness of the film, and the rate at which the torsion necessary for tearing of the film increases with time is a measure of the rate of growth of film. He concluded that the dyestuffs which in solution, show photo-electric effect, have the characteristic property of forming a film on the surface, the maximum photo-electric effect being obtained when the film thickness becomes maximum.

It appears that if a method could be devised for recording the variation of surface tension of these aqueous solutions of dyestuffs with time, some insight can be gained into the kinetics of the molecular processes which are responsible for producing a film on the surface. It is to be expected that with the growth of film on the surface, the surface tension of the solution should gradually diminish arriving at a constant value when the growth of the film is at an end.

Indications are not wanting that the nature of the surface of a solution immediately after it is created is different from that of the surface after a certain time has elapsed and conditions of equilibrium have been established. This is specially true in the case of hydrophylic sols like sodium oleate, gelatine, egg-albumin, saponin, etc. For these sols, the investigations of Rayleigh (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1890, 47, 281) and Berczeller (*Intern. Z. physik-chem. Biol.*, 1914, 1, 124) have shown that the surface tension measured by a dynamic method—where the surface tension of a freshly created surface is measured—is always considerably greater than that measured by a static method. The reason for this difference is not far to seek. In a freshly created surface of these sols, the surface concentration of the micellæ is initially very small, much below the equilibrium surface concentration; and since the velocity of translation of these micellæ is much smaller than that of truly dissolved substances, the time required to reach static equilibrium at the surface is fairly long. Though the dynamic and static methods of measuring surface tension reveal that in case some hydrophylic sols static equilibrium at

the surface is reached fairly slowly, no method has yet been devised for recording in these cases the rate of change of surface tension as the fresh surface gradually ages and reaches equilibrium conditions.

It is well known that aqueous solutions of many dyestuffs of very large molecular weight cannot be considered as true molecularly dispersed solutions. There is strong evidence of micellæ formation in many cases, and it is therefore to be expected that in these cases also, the freshly created surface should have a much larger surface tension than a surface which has been formed for a considerable time.

According to Freundlich "the method of adhesion of rings is to be particularly recommended for determining the surface tension of any plane liquid surface which it is desired to disturb as little as possible." In the experiments to be described in the following pages, the ring method has been suitably modified to yield values of surface tension of a surface at different intervals of time, not only without actually breaking the surface but also without disturbing the surface to any considerable extent.

EXPERIMENTAL.

To obtain accurate and satisfactory results, it is necessary to have a balance in which the weights required to counterbalance the forces of surface tension could be continuously but very slowly increased. From one end of the balance beam (Fig. 1) was therefore

Fig. 1.

hung a fine gold chain; the other end of this chain was fastened to a vertical rod which could be moved up and down by means of a rack and pinion arrangement. A pointer attached to this vertical rod reads off its position against a vertical scale. The weight required to counterbalance the chain in different positions, was determined. The balance pan at *A* was replaced by an exactly circular basin *B* made of thin nickel plate. Suspension was effected by means of a copper rod soldered to the centre of the plate. The basin was so made that the lower rim, which was to touch the liquid surface, lay exactly in a horizontal plane when suspended from the hook *A*. In order that readings might be taken always at the same level of the surface of the solution, a cathetometer *T* was used for observing the height of the surface. It was found that in course of several hours the level of the surface fell due to evaporation. To avoid this difficulty water at about 40° in a large vessel was placed inside the balance case. The evaporation from this surface kept the humidity in the balance almost at saturation. The level of the solution remained constant without the temperature fluctuating more than 0.5° during the course of the experiment.

A glass beaker containing water was placed beneath the inverted nickel basin, the balance beam freed from arrestment, and when oscillations had ceased, water was poured in until the lower rim completely touched the surface of the water. Weights were then added to the other end of the balance beam, the final additions being made by lowering the chain. The pointer attached to the balance remained motionless until a critical weight has been added when it began to move to the left, indicating that the weight has counterbalanced the forces of surface tension. This motion is slow and the ring is not suddenly torn off the liquid surface. *The weight was recorded when balance pointer was just moving towards the left and then the weight was slightly diminished by raising up the chain, The surface tension was thus measured without actually breaking the surface and with the minimum disturbance of the molecular arrangement of the surface.*

All the precautions necessary for obtaining accurate data were taken. For example, conductivity water was always used. The glass vessels, and the nickel basin were washed alternately with acids and alkali and finally with conductivity water and were dried inside a desiccator. Merck's pure dyestuffs were used in every case. In the case of Rhodamine B however, a small fraction of the

solid did not dissolve. Rhodamin B was therefore obtained as shining greenish crystals by crystallisation from a solution of pure alcohol.

The surface tension was calculated as follows:—

$$\text{Surface tension of the solution} = \frac{\sigma \times W_2}{W_1},$$

where σ = Surface tension of water at the temperature of the experiment.

W_2 = Weight required to raise the basin from the surface of the solution.

W_1 = Weight required to raise the basin from the surface of water.

In the case of solutions of some of the dyestuffs in water, the surface tension diminished with time, attaining a constant value after some 4 or 5 hours, depending on the nature of the dyestuff as well as on the concentration of the solution.

Results.

Table I shows the results obtained for the surface tension σ of the solutions investigated at various times t (in minutes) reckoned from the time at which the first observation was made. It will be seen that in the case of water and of aqueous solutions of Diamond fuchsin and Methylene blue, the surface tension does not change with time.

TABLE I.

Substance.	Temp.	Conc. in gm. mol. per litre.	t_1	σ	t_2	σ	t_3	σ
Pure water ...	28°	—	0	72·08	180	72·08	360	72·08
Diamond fuchsin ...	20°	0·000467	0	72·28	120	72·28		
		0·000804	0	71·73	120	71·7		
		0·00588	0	70·75	120	70·7		
Methylene blue ...	30°	0·000467	0	70·63	120	70·6		
		0·0022	0	70·6	120	70·6		
		0·0055	0	70·6	120	70·6		

In Table II, $K_{1.2}$, $K_{1.3}$, $K_{1.4}$ are the values of K_7 (K_7 in Eqn. 8) calculated from the first and second, first and third, and first and fourth observations respectively. σ_∞ denotes the limiting value of σ usually reached after 4 or 5 hours.

Discussion.

The fact that in the case of solutions of Methylene blue and fuchsine, the surface tension, as measured by the experimental method described above, did not vary with time, whereas in the case of the other solutions (Rhodamine B, Crystal violet, Bismark brown, Malachite green) there, was observed a considerable diminution of surface tension with time is, in itself, a strong evidence in favour of the validity of this method for measuring variation of surface tension with time. It will be noted that the lowering of surface tension in the case of the latter group of dyestuffs, for similar concentrations is very much greater than in the case of the former group. The magnitude of this lowering is so large that these solutions may be classed with soap solutions.

When a surface of such a solution is freshly made, the surface concentration of the solute is small. The surface concentration of the micellæ increases with time until the maximum surface concentration corresponding to the particular strength of the solution is reached. The rate of condensation of micellæ on the surface from the bulk of the liquid = $K_1 C (1 - a)$, where C is the bulk concentration and a is the fraction of surface already covered with micellæ ... (1)

The rate of removal of micellæ into the bulk of the solution from the surface = $K_2 a$... (2)

The rate of increase of surface concentration C of micellæ

$$\frac{dC_s}{dt} = K_1 C (1 - a) - K_2 a$$

where C_s is the surface concentration of micellæ.

$$\text{or} \quad \frac{dC_s}{dt} = K_1 C - [K_1 C + K_2] a$$

When the volume of the solution is large, the bulk concentration C does not perceptibly change due to the ingress of micellæ into the surface. Again a may be taken as proportional to the actual surface concentration at any time. Hence

$$\frac{dC_s}{dt} = K_3 - K_4 C_s \quad \dots (3)$$

According to the ideas of Langmuir and Traube, the lowering of surface tension in solution

$$\sigma_0 - \sigma_s = F = RTC_s \quad \dots (4)$$

where σ_0 = the surface tension of the pure solvent,

σ_s = the surface tension of the solution,

F = the two dimensional gas pressure exerted by the solute molecules in excess at the interface.

Hence at a constant temperature T , $\frac{dC_s}{dt} = \frac{1}{RT} \cdot \frac{dF}{dt} \left(C_s = \frac{F}{RT} \right)$

or $\frac{1}{RT} \cdot \frac{dF}{dt} = K_3 - \frac{K_4}{Rt} F$ (from 3) ... (5)

or $\log_e \frac{F_\infty}{F_\infty - F} = K_6 t$... (6)

where F_∞ is the the value of F when $t = \infty$

or $\frac{1}{t_2 - t_1} \log_e \frac{F_\infty - Ft_1}{F_\infty - Ft_2} = K_6$... (7)

or $\frac{2.3}{t_2 - t_1} \log_{10} \frac{\sigma_{t_1} - \sigma_{t_\infty}}{\sigma_{t_2} - \sigma_{t_\infty}} = K_7$... (8)

Where σ_{t_1} , σ_{t_2} and σ_{t_∞} are the surface tensions of solution of constant bulk concentration at t_1 , t_2 and t_∞ respectively.

The value of K_7 has been given as $K_{1.2}$, $K_{1.3}$ and $K_{1.4}$ in Table II. It will be noticed that for each dyestuff the value of K_7 is within the range of experimental error, a constant, independent of the concentration of the dyestuff. This is to be expected from the theory developed above. The value of K_7 for each dyestuff is summarised in the following table.

TABLE III.

Dyestuff.	K_1 (mean).
Crystal violet	... 0'0133
Rhodamine B	... 0'00667
Bismarck brown	.. 0'0119
Malachite green	... 0'0253

We have thus been able to obtain a picture of the kinetic processes according to which the large molecules of the above dyes come to the surface from the bulk of the solution, and it is satisfactory to note that the quantitative equation developed on the basis of these kinetic processes, explains fairly accurately the variation of surface tension of the solutions of these organic dyes with time.

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